

Quantum Mechanics and the Doppler Effect

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For sound and light, changes in energy due to moving frames are manifested in terms of a change in frequency as energy itself is identified with frequency. On the other hand, the energy of photons and phonons is given by $E=pc$ which follows from the more general Einstein energy momentum equation $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ ((1)). A solution for $m_0=0$ $E=pc$ is to set $E=i\hbar d/dt$ and $p=-i\hbar d/dx$ with both operating on $\exp(-ipx+iEt)$. This begs the question as to the meaning of this exponential function. It matches the solution of the sound wave equation: $d/dt d/dt$ (partial) density $+cc d/dx d/dx$ density = 0, but $E=pc$ is a different equation. Thus, we argue that $\exp(-ipx+iEt)$ has a different meaning than density(x)=Probability(x). As deBroglie showed in the 1920s, one may suggest that matter particles (e.g. electrons) also have a frequency (and wavelength) and satisfy ((1)) in analogy to phonons and photons. Using $E=i\hbar d/dt$ (partial) and $p=-i\hbar d/dx$ in ((1)) yields the Klein-Gordon quantum equation from which the Schrodinger equation follows in the low kinetic energy limit. One may note that $\exp(-ipx+iEt)$ may interfere if added to $\exp(-ipx+iEt + \text{phase shift})$ as shown in electron interference experiments. Thus, having $px-Et$ as a Lorentz invariant is essential. There is not only a "doppler" shift, but an interference result with no particles at a point x and t and this maps into the same physical result for x',t' in a boosted frame. Thus, the idea of $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ seems to be closely linked to Lorentz invariance.

A bigger issue occurs if one considers the Dirac form of the energy-momentum equation: $(E-V)(E+V) = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ ((2)). It is possible to use the simple approximation of $V(x_0) = \text{constant}$ at each x_0 and consider an $\exp(i p(x_0) x_0 - iEt)$. Given the idea of superposition, however, one may consider $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$. This then leads to a solution of ((2)) with $E=i\hbar d/dt$, $p=-i\hbar d/dx$, of $W(x,t)=\exp(iEt) \text{ Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. At this point, $\exp(ipx)$ is a relative probability $P(p/x)$.

We try to investigate these ideas further in this note.

$E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ ((1))

It is well-known that the Einstein momentum-energy equation describes both relativistic particles with mass m_0 (such as electrons), but also photons and phonons ($m_0=0$). Photons and phonons, however, have a "frequency" proportional to their energy and may undergo interference (superposition). This immediately begs the question of whether "frequency" should only be restricted to particles with no rest mass. It may be noted that for a particle with m_0 , $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. If m_0 is very small, one might expect that "momentum energy" should represent frequency as in the case of $m_0=0$. In fact, deBroglie in the 1920s suggested that particles with a rest mass (like electrons) should have a frequency and wavelength .

With the development of the non-relativistic Schrodinger equation: $i\hbar d/dt W = H W$ ((3)), it was noted historically that ((3)) utilizes d/dt and not $d/dt d/dt$ as in wave equations for strings or sound. This was considered a major difference with wave theory, even though solutions for zero potential for the Schrodinger and wave equations match i.e. they are sinusoidal.

We argue in this note, that from ((1)) an equation which utilizes only $i\partial/\partial t$ also applies to phonons and photons i.e. $i\partial/\partial t W = -i\partial/\partial x W$ with $W(x,t) = \exp(iEt) \exp(-ipx)$. For a material particle in the nonrelativistic limit: $i\partial/\partial t W = -1/2m \partial^2/\partial x^2 W$. Thus, both have a frequency E manifested in $\exp(-iEt)$.

This in turn leads to a wavelength as well which is manifested in $\exp(ipx)$ with $p = E/v$ wavelength. As a result, both material and zero rest mass particles satisfy ((1)) and also have a frequency and wavelength.

Lorentz Invariance

One may note that the solution $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ contains the Lorentz invariant $px - Et$. This is critical because interference or superposition of different $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ (same p , different phase shifts) may lead to a "real" (non-complex) solution of peaks and troughs as in interference experiments. A trough cannot disappear if one performs a Lorentz boost and so invariance is needed. It is interesting to point out that Lorentz invariance is present in the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation because $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ is still a solution for a free particle. (The Schrodinger equation is also invariant under boosts. (1)). It is only the nonrelativistic form of the energy which is used. Thus, there seem to be two ideas. First, one has a frequency equal to energy (for a free quantum particle or even a bound state solution). Secondly, there is an energy conservation equation which uses operators $i\partial/\partial t$ (partial) and $-i\partial/\partial x$ to describe E and p .

Effect of a Potential

The meaning of $\exp(ipx - iEt)$, which at this point is solely a math solution of ((1)) if E and p are replaced with $i\partial/\partial t$ and $-i\partial/\partial x$, is still not clear. Matters become more confusing if one introduces a potential $V(x)$ which leads to the Dirac form of the energy-momentum equation:

$$(E - V)(E - V) = p^2 + m_0^2 \quad ((4))$$

At this point, one no longer thinks in terms of photons and phonons, but strictly in terms of a relativistic classical particle which interacts with $V(x)$ i.e. is accelerated. Given ((4)), one might at first think that all links to energy as a frequency and photons and phonons are gone. Certainly, $V(x)$ is taken directly from classical mechanics. Potentials, however, do exist for wave phenomena, as water waves may change frequency due to water depth.

Thus, it seems that it is critical to determine how $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ enters into ((4)). As a simple approximation, which is sometimes used, one may consider $V(x_0) = \text{constant}$ at each x_0 and find a corresponding $\exp(i p(x_0)x_0 - i Et)$. An alternative idea is to consider superposition (interference) and suggest that $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$. This leads to quite a different picture of the classical potential. It is only $V(x)$ on average, and one no longer considers acceleration as a particle moves from x_1, t_1 to x_2, t_2 . Rather, ((4)) has a solution of:

$$W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt) \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

This indicates that $\exp(ipx)$ plays the role of a relative (unnormalized) probability and that the presence of a potential means a free quantum particle momentum distribution at each x . Classical conservation only exists on “average” i.e.

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V W = E W \quad ((6))$$

Dividing by W , yields a first term which is average kinetic and exactly equals the classical result In the form of ((6)), however, one sees clearly the interaction of $V(x)$ (decomposed) with the momentum distribution. It is interesting to note that $W(x,t)$ interacts with $V(x)$, but also serves the role of a normalizing factor for the momentum probability distribution. This carries over into the relativistic Klein Gordon case because the operator form of $(E-V)(E-V) = p^2 + m_0^2$ operates on $W(x,t)$. For $W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt)W(x)$. In such a case W factors out of all terms except p^2 so one has:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \left(-\frac{d}{dx} \right) W(x) / W(x) \text{ which is an average value and all other terms are free of } W(x)$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we wish to show that given $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ ((1)), one may obtain a solution for $m_0=0$ i.e. $E=pc$. Given that phonons and photons exhibit wave type behaviour, a solution of this equation is $E=i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$, $p=-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x}$ operating on $\exp(ipx-iEt)$. Given that the density wave equation for a sound wave contains $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt}$ and $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$, this is not an equation for $P(x)$. Nevertheless, $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ captures the wave behaviour properly and following deBroglie one may postulate that such a wave (i.e. energy as frequency) could be applied to ((1)) with m_0 non zero. This again leads to an $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ solution with interference possible. The Lorentz invariant $px-Et$ ensures that interference patterns hold in different frames.

A more difficult issue is dealing with ((1)) with a potential i.e. $(E-V)(E-V) = p^2 + m_0^2$. Given the idea of superposition and also the notion that $V(x)$ is really appropriate for classical mechanics, one may suggest: $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. This leads to $\exp(ipx-Et)$ being replaced with the solution $\exp(-iEt) \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. In other words, one has a momentum distribution, but still an energy frequency. The momentum distribution, however, is composed of $\exp(ipx)$ for free quantum particles and suggests that $\exp(ipx)$ is a conditional probability related to $P(p/x)$.

References

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